

Amyand's Hernia Presenting as an Incarcerated Inguinoscrotal Hernia: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Background: Amyand's hernia is a rare condition characterized by the presence of the vermiform appendix within an inguinal hernia sac. Its incidence is low, and its association with acute appendicitis is even rarer, often leading to diagnostic difficulty. Most cases are diagnosed intraoperatively, particularly when presenting as an incarcerated or strangulated hernia.

Case Presentation: We report the case of a 66-year-old man with a 30-year history of untreated right inguinoscrotal hernia who presented with acute scrotal pain and signs of intestinal obstruction. Physical examination revealed a painful, non-reducible right inguinoscrotal mass. Laboratory studies showed elevated inflammatory markers. Computed tomography demonstrated an incarcerated right inguinal hernia containing bowel loops. Emergency surgical exploration was performed. Intraoperatively, an inflamed appendix with a periappendiceal abscess was identified within the hernia sac. Appendectomy, abscess drainage, and herniorrhaphy were successfully performed. The postoperative course was uneventful, and the patient was discharged in good clinical condition. Histopathological examination confirmed acute nonspecific appendicitis without perforation.

Conclusion: Amyand's hernia complicated by acute appendicitis is an uncommon surgical finding that may mimic an incarcerated inguinal hernia. Early surgical intervention and individualized management based on intraoperative findings are essential to achieve favorable outcomes.

KEYWORDS: Amyand's hernia; Acute appendicitis; Inguinoscrotal hernia; Case report; Emergency surgery

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INTRODUCTION

Amyand's hernia is an uncommon clinical entity defined by the presence of the vermiform appendix within an inguinal hernia sac. Its occurrence accounts for approximately <1% of all inguinal hernia cases, and its complication with acute appendicitis is even rarer, estimated at 0.1–0.3% of all hernias and appendicitis cases, respectively.

First described by Claudius Amyand in 1735, when a perforated appendix was found within an inguinal hernia sac during surgery, this condition represents a unique diagnostic and therapeutic challenge due to its atypical presentation.

Patients with Amyand's hernia typically present with symptoms indistinguishable from those of an incarcerated inguinal hernia, which frequently leads to a preoperative misdiagnosis. The definitive diagnosis is often made

intraoperatively or, less commonly, by imaging such as computed tomography or ultrasonography.

The management of Amyand's hernia with acute appendicitis requires individualized surgical decision-making, as the inflammatory state of the appendix and the presence of contamination influence the choice between performing *appendectomy* and the type of hernia repair, especially regarding the use of mesh.

Because of its rare occurrence and lack of specific clinical features, reporting additional cases and reviewing the literature enhances understanding of optimal diagnostic approaches and surgical management strategies.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 66-year-old man presented to the emergency department with a 15-day history of progressive right scrotal pain that

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began after physical exertion and was initially self-managed with analgesics. His medical history was significant for a right inguinoscrotal hernia of approximately 30 years' duration without prior surgical treatment, type 2 diabetes mellitus diagnosed one year earlier and managed with metformin (850 mg daily), as well as long-standing alcohol and tobacco abuse.

Forty-eight hours prior to admission, the pain intensified and became refractory to analgesics, accompanied by signs of intestinal obstruction, including absence of bowel movements and flatus. The patient also developed anorexia, fever, nausea, and five episodes of vomiting, prompting hospital evaluation. On physical examination, the patient was conscious and oriented, with evident pain distress. Cardiopulmonary examination was unremarkable. The abdomen was semi-globose due to adipose tissue, with increased bowel sounds, soft and depressible, but tender to palpation in the right iliac fossa and hypogastrium, with signs of peritoneal irritation. Genital examination revealed a non-reducible, painful enlargement of the right hemiscrotum with erythema and visible peristalsis.

Laboratory studies on admission showed a white blood cell count of $9.3 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$, hemoglobin level of 13.2 g/dL, serum glucose of 129 mg/dL, C-reactive protein of 50.4 mg/L, and lactate dehydrogenase of 315 U/L. Other laboratory parameters were within normal limits.

A contrast-enhanced computed tomography scan of the abdomen and pelvis demonstrated a 4.5-cm defect in the right inguinal canal, through which the cecum, ascending colon, ileal loops, and adipose tissue protruded. Mild fat stranding was noted, and a large hernia sac measuring $13.3 \times 9.4 \times 22$ cm extended into the ipsilateral scrotum, consistent with an incarcerated inguinal hernia.

The patient was taken emergently to the operating room. An infraumbilical midline laparotomy was initially performed, revealing the cecum and small bowel within the hernia sac; however, reduction of the herniated contents was unsuccessful. Consequently, an additional inguinal approach was undertaken. Upon opening the hernia sac, inflammatory fluid was encountered, along with adherent small and large bowel loops and an inflamed appendix with a periappendiceal abscess contained within the hernia sac. An appendectomy and abscess drainage were performed, followed by successful reduction of the hernia contents. Herniorrhaphy was completed, a drain was placed extending into the pelvic cavity, and the abdominal wall was closed in layers.

Postoperatively, the patient was monitored in the hospital ward. Oral intake was initiated 12 hours after surgery and was well tolerated, with return of bowel function evidenced by passage of flatus and bowel movements. The drain produced minimal serohematic output. The patient remained afebrile and showed no signs of systemic inflammatory response, allowing discharge home in improved clinical condition.

Histopathological examination revealed mild acute nonspecific appendicitis without evidence of perforation. At

outpatient follow-up two weeks later, the patient demonstrated satisfactory clinical recovery without complications.

DISCUSSION

Amyand's hernia represents a rare subtype of inguinal hernia in which the vermiform appendix is contained within the hernia sac. The condition is encountered in <1% of inguinal hernia repairs, and the presence of acute appendicitis within the hernia sac occurs even less frequently, estimated at 0.1–0.3% in reported cohorts.

Clinically, this pathology often mimics other causes of groin swelling and pain, typically presenting as an irreducible or incarcerated inguinal hernia, making preoperative distinction difficult. Imaging modalities such as ultrasound and CT scans may aid in diagnosis, though many cases are identified incidentally during surgical exploration. Ultrasound findings may show a blind-ended tubular structure within the hernia sac, while CT can precisely delineate hernia content and inflammation.

The decision-making process surrounding the surgical approach in Amyand's hernia is informed by both the Losanoff–Basson classification and intraoperative findings. In cases where the appendix is inflamed or perforated (type II or III), appendectomy and hernia repair should be performed without mesh to minimize the risk of prosthetic infection. In contrast, when the appendix is normal (type I), some authors advocate mesh repair without appendectomy.

Several reported cases illustrate the spectrum of presentation and management. A recent case in an elderly female highlighted the occurrence of perforated appendicitis within an Amyand's hernia managed with percutaneous abscess drainage followed by interval laparoscopic appendectomy, demonstrating alternative approaches tailored to patient comorbidities. Another report described successful reduction and appendectomy under local anesthesia for gangrenous appendicitis within the sac, emphasizing the variability in surgical strategy.

The literature underscores that although Amyand's hernia with acute appendicitis is rare, surgeons should include it in the differential diagnosis of incarcerated inguinal hernias, particularly in older patients. Advances in imaging have improved preoperative diagnosis, but the condition often remains a surgical surprise.

Finally, reporting of such cases with detailed operative management and outcomes contributes to a growing body of evidence that informs best practices in treating this uncommon pathology.

CONCLUSION

Amyand's hernia is a rare surgical entity that often presents as an incarcerated inguinal or inguinoscrotal hernia, making preoperative diagnosis challenging. The presence of acute appendicitis within the hernia sac further increases diagnostic and therapeutic complexity and is frequently identified only

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during surgical exploration. This case highlights the importance of maintaining a high index of suspicion for unusual hernia contents in patients presenting with acute scrotal pain and signs of intestinal obstruction.

Prompt surgical intervention remains essential to prevent complications such as perforation, abscess formation, and sepsis. Management should be individualized based on intraoperative findings, particularly regarding the condition of the appendix and the degree of contamination, which directly influence the decision to perform appendectomy and the type of hernia repair. Reporting rare presentations such as this contributes to the existing literature and supports improved recognition and optimal surgical management of Amyand's hernia in emergency settings.

ETHICS APPROVAL AND CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE

Ethical approval was not required for this case report according to institutional policies. Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and accompanying images.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this article.

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